

Prospective Study on Clinical Profile and Outcome Predictors of Acute Kidney Injury in Indian Patients

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Abstract:

Background: Acute Kidney Injury (AKI) is a severe clinical syndrome associated with high hospital mortality. However, limited prospective data exist on the long-term outcomes of AKI. This study was conducted to assess the clinical profiles and factors influencing outcomes in patients with AKI over a follow-up period.

Materials and Methods: A prospective study was conducted from August 2024 to November 2024, enrolling 80 participants with AKI as defined by the Kidney Disease Improving Global Outcomes (KDIGO) criteria. Data on demographics, clinical features, and etiological factors were collected. Patients were followed for three months, and univariate and multinomial analyses were used to predict outcomes. A Cox regression model was applied to identify predictors of mortality.

Results: The mean age of the participants was 41.67 ± 16.21 years, with a male predominance. Most patients (81.9%) required non-ICU care. Oliguria was observed in 36% of cases, and 39.6% required dialysis. Sepsis was the most common single etiology. The majority of patients were categorized as KDIGO stage 3, followed by stage 2. At three months, 40.6% achieved complete recovery, 12.3% had partial recovery, 4.2% showed no recovery, and 30.4% succumbed to the condition. Mortality was significantly associated with factors such as age, single etiology, hepatorenal syndrome, sepsis, need for mechanical ventilation and vasopressors, comorbidities, and glomerulonephritis.

Conclusion: AKI is associated with substantial mortality, even among patients who initially present with non-ICU care needs. These findings emphasize the importance of AKI prevention, early detection, and timely intervention to address reversible risk factors and improve clinical outcomes.

Keywords: Nephrology, AKI, Kidney and Sepsis.

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Introduction

Acute kidney injury (AKI) is a significant complication in acutely ill patients, contributing substantially to global mortality and morbidity. AKI can be present at the time of hospital admission or develop during hospitalization [1]. In tropical countries like India, AKI which occurs outside the hospital setting, is often linked to dehydration, diarrhea, infections, venomous snakebites, and other factors. Within the Indian subcontinent, there is considerable geographical variation in the reported causes of AKI.

Over time, the etiological spectrum has evolved, encompassing conditions such as malaria, sepsis, nephrotoxic drugs, and liver disease, as well as diarrhea, glomerulonephritis, snakebites, and leptospirosis[2]. AKI is a prevalent and often severe clinical syndrome associated with high in-hospital mortality rates. Among survivors, severe AKI requiring dialysis frequently leads to incomplete recovery or progression to chronic

kidney disease (CKD) [3]. Patients who develop AKI face a significant risk of CKD progression within one year of hospitalization, even in less severe cases of AKI. Recent evidence suggests that even patients with apparent complete recovery from AKI remain at an elevated risk of developing CKD over time. This underscores the need for continued monitoring and proactive management to mitigate long-term complications [3,4].

Significant gaps remain in our understanding of the pathophysiology and clinical course of AKI that does not resolve. Competing risk factors must be considered when assessing recovery patterns, yet many available studies are limited by small sample sizes, regional focus, and the inability to account for key confounding factors such as proteinuria. Furthermore, these studies often fail to provide a comprehensive characterization of renal outcome patterns [5]. The timing of renal function recovery following AKI is crucial, as delayed recovery is

associated with a higher risk of long-term progression to CKD and impacts overall survival rates. Despite the pressing need to improve outcomes for patients with partial or non-recovery from AKI, the literature on follow-up data for these patients is sparse[6,7].

Moreover, few studies from developing countries address AKI, with the majority focusing on hospital-acquired AKI. To bridge these gaps, this study aims to evaluate the risk factors for developing AKI, the patterns of renal recovery, and their associated three-month outcomes.

Materials and Methods

This prospective observational study was conducted at Swaminarayan Institute of Medical Sciences and Research, a tertiary-level hospital located in Kalol, Ahmedabad. The study was approved by the institutional ethics committee, and informed consent was obtained from all participants. Patients aged 18 years or older who met the AKI criteria defined by the Kidney Disease Improving Global Outcomes (KDIGO) guidelines were included in the study. AKI was identified if AKI was present at the time of hospital presentation or developed within 48 hours of admission. Exclusion criteria included patients with pre-existing chronic kidney disease (CKD), probable CKD evidenced by surrogate markers or imaging findings of structural abnormalities, bilaterally reduced kidney size (<8.5 cm), or those already on any form of renal replacement therapy (RRT).

Patients were recruited for the study through nephrology consultations referred from various hospital departments. The inclusion criteria encompassed both outpatients and inpatients from the nephrology department, as well as individuals referred from other wards. Data collection utilized structured proformas and data abstraction checklists. Information gathered included patient demographics, diagnoses, associated comorbidities, and laboratory investigation results such as creatinine, urea, electrolytes, complete blood count, and liver function tests.

All patients underwent kidney ultrasonography to assess size and detect structural abnormalities. Additional investigations were conducted as clinically indicated. For patients presenting with signs or symptoms of sepsis, blood and other cultures were collected as necessary. Patients showing features suggestive of glomerular diseases (e.g., hypertension, proteinuria, and hematuria) underwent further immunological and other specialized investigations to guide their management.

All participants were followed up and assessed for outcomes at three time points: day 7, 1 month, and 3 months. Clinical examination findings were

recorded during each follow-up, including the quantification of urine output through 24-hour urinary volume measurement. Laboratory parameters, such as serum creatinine levels, were monitored. Urine analysis was conducted to detect the presence of proteinuria and microscopic hematuria.

The following outcome variables were used: Complete Recovery (CR): Serum creatinine returned to baseline values (if baseline values were available). If baseline values were unavailable, CR was defined as a decrease in serum creatinine to ≤ 1 mg/dL. The choice of the 1 mg/dL cut-off was based on the assumption that this level typically corresponds to a glomerular filtration rate (GFR) above 60 mL/min in adults across various age groups. This criterion was pragmatically selected for the study setting and supported by references where GFR calculations might not always be accessible. Partial Recovery (PR): Serum creatinine did not return to baseline or remained >1 mg/dL but decreased to <4 mg/dL (aligned with KDIGO stage 3 criteria, using 4 mg/dL as the cut-off). The patient did not require dialysis. Non-Recovery (NR): Serum creatinine remained >4 mg/dL without dialysis requirements, or the patient required dialysis support. Death: The patient succumbed during the follow-up period.

Baseline creatinine was defined as the value of serum creatinine (in mg/dL) available from 8 days to 12 months prior to the current presentation with CA-AKI. In the absence of studies validating serum creatinine or GFR imputation in the Indian population, an empirical serum creatinine cutoff was used. For defining non-recovery (NR), a serum creatinine level >4 mg/dL was chosen, as this is considered a severe form of AKI according to KDIGO criteria. A creatinine level above 4 mg/dL in any adult was classified as advanced renal dysfunction. At each follow-up visit, patients were assessed for their outcome status. The study endpoints were the achievement of complete recovery (CR) or patient death.

Data entry was performed using Microsoft Excel, and analysis was conducted using Epi Info software version 7.2.2.2. The normality of data distribution was assessed using the Kolmogorov–Smirnov test. Baseline characteristics and patterns of AKI were presented as frequencies and percentages, while quantitative data were expressed as means \pm standard deviation (SD).

A bar diagram was used to display the pattern of AKI outcomes at each follow-up period. Univariable Cox regression was performed to evaluate the effects of potential factors on overall survival. Variables with a p-value <0.05 in the univariable analysis were included in the multivariable analysis. A reduced model was

selected using Akaike's Information Criterion (AIC) to build the final multivariate model. Multinomial logistic regression was used to calculate the adjusted odds ratio (AOR) following univariate analysis of overall patient outcomes. A p-value <0.05 was considered statistically significant for all analyses.

Results

Baseline and clinical characteristics of the study participants. The mean age of the participants was

41.67 ± 16.21 years. Most participants, with a male predominance, were in the 18–45 age range. Comorbidities were observed in approximately 27% of patients, with hypertension and diabetes being the most common conditions. The majority of participants required non-ICU care and were admitted to either the nephrology or medicine wards.

Baseline creatinine levels were available for only 11 patients (Table 1).

Table 1: Baseline and clinical characteristics of AKI patients (n = 80)

Variables	n (%) / Mean ± SD
Age (years)	41.67 ± 16.21
18–45 years	48 (60.7)
46–60 years	20 (26.1)
≥61 years	10 (12.5)
Male gender	45 (56.2)
Associated comorbidities	35 (27.9)
Diabetes mellitus	10 (12)
Hypertension	13 (15.5)
Cardiovascular disease	3 (3.2)
Cerebrovascular accident	2 (1.8)
Place of admission	
Non-ICU	65 (81.9)
ICU	14 (18.1)
Causes	
Medical	61 (77.1)
Surgical	17 (21.2)
Obstetric	1 (1.7)
Type of AKI	
Oliguria	29 (36.0)
Non-oliguria	51 (64.0)
KDIGO stage	
Stage 1	18 (14.5)
Stage 2	36 (29.3)
Stage 3	70 (56.2)
AKI etiology	
Single	51 (64.7)
Multiple	43 (35.3)
Patient on mechanical ventilator support	112 (5.5)
RRT requirement	31 (39.6)

The majority of participants presented with oliguric AKI. As per KDIGO definitions, stage 3 AKI was the most commonly observed at diagnosis, followed by stage 2 and stage 1.

Most patients had a single etiology of AKI, with sepsis being the leading cause, followed by

hypovolemia and glomerulonephritis. Mechanical ventilatory (MV) support was required by 15.5% of patients, while renal replacement therapy (RRT) was needed by 39.6%.

Table 2 presents the various potential causes of AKI among the study participants.

Table 2: Causes of AKI

Causes of AKI	Frequency, n (%)
Pre-renal	
Volume loss	61 (21.6)
Gastrointestinal	39 (13.8)
Third space	13 (4.6)
Skin	6 (2.2)

Renal	
Evidence of shock	
Septic shock	54 (19.1)
Hypovolemic shock	32 (11.3)
Cardiogenic shock	12 (4.2)
Cardiorenal syndrome	17 (6)
Hepatorenal syndrome	9 (3.2)
Renal	
Sepsis-associated	44(55.8)
Glomerulonephritis	52 (18.4)
Drug-induced	28 (9.9)
Rhabdomyolysis	13 (4.6)
Post-renal	
Calculus	9 (3.2)
Non-calculi	3 (1.1)

A significant prevalence of sepsis was observed, with 6 cases showing identifiable initial foci. The gastrointestinal tract emerged as the most common site (30.4%), followed by the urinary tract (17.1%) and sepsis with an unspecified organ focus (16.5%). The respiratory tract and skin contributed 13.9% and 13.3%, respectively. The female genital tract, musculoskeletal system, and infective endocarditis accounted for 5.7%, 2.5%, and 0.6%, respectively.

The distribution of nephrotoxic drugs among the studied population revealed various contributors to renal impairment. Non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) were the most prevalent, accounting for 46.3% of cases, followed by alternative medications (17.9%), antitubercular drugs (7.1%),

and other drugs, each contributing to one case. Figure 1 presents a schematic overview of AKI patient outcomes at various follow-up intervals. At the initial assessment on day seven, only 13.4% of patients had achieved complete recovery, with this percentage increasing to 40.6% by the third month. Partial recovery and non-recovery rates decreased over time.

By the third month, 40.6%, 12.7%, and 4.2% of participants had complete, partial, and non-recovery, respectively. Mortality rates were 24.4%, 29.0%, and 30.4% at the 7-day, 1-month, and 3-month follow-ups, respectively. When glomerulonephritis (GN) patients were excluded, mortality rates were 28.1%, 32.5%, and 32.9% at the 7-day, 1-month, and 3-month follow-ups, respectively.

Figure 1: Distribution of study participants based on the patient outcome on 7 days, 1 month and 3-month follow-up. CR: complete recovery; PR: partial recovery; FR: failure to recover; LFU: Lost to follow-up.

Univariate Cox regression analysis identified several factors associated with mortality among AKI patients. Age between 18 to 30 years (HR =

0.291, $p < 0.001$) and 31 to 45 years (HR = 0.534, $p = 0.034$), a single etiology (HR = 0.482, $p = 0.001$), the presence of glomerulonephritis (HR = 0.489, p

= 0.034), and higher serum protein (HR = 0.805, p = 0.01) and albumin levels (HR = 0.723, p = 0.007) were associated with a reduced risk of mortality. Conversely, the presence of hepatorenal syndrome (HR = 3.801, p < 0.001), sepsis (HR = 2.606, p < 0.001), comorbidities (HR = 1.594, p = 0.035), and the requirement for mechanical ventilation (HR = 3.861, p < 0.001) and vasopressors (HR = 3.299, p < 0.001) were linked to an increased risk of death.

These statistically significant risk factors were then subjected to multivariate Cox regression. The results presented in Table 3 indicate that the adjusted hazard ratio (AHR) was significant for two factors: the presence of hepatorenal syndrome (AHR = 3.570, p = 0.006) and the requirement for ventilatory support (AHR = 2.406, p = 0.013).

Predictors of mortality: The univariate Cox regression analysis identified several factors associated with mortality in patients with Acute Kidney Injury (AKI). Protective factors included younger age groups, with patients aged 18 to 30 years (HR = 0.291, p < 0.001) and 31 to 45 years (HR = 0.534, p = 0.034) having significantly lower risks of mortal-

ity. Additionally, a single etiology of AKI (HR = 0.482, p = 0.001), the presence of glomerulonephritis (HR = 0.489, p = 0.034), and higher serum protein (HR = 0.805, p = 0.01) and albumin levels (HR = 0.723, p = 0.007) were found to be associated with reduced mortality risk. In contrast, factors associated with increased mortality included the presence of hepatorenal syndrome (HR = 3.801, p < 0.001), sepsis (HR = 2.606, p < 0.001), comorbidities (HR = 1.594, p = 0.035), and the need for mechanical ventilation (HR = 3.861, p < 0.001) or vasopressors (HR = 3.299, p < 0.001). Subsequently, a multivariate Cox regression analysis was conducted to adjust for these factors, and it revealed that only two factors remained significantly associated with mortality. The presence of hepatorenal syndrome (AHR = 3.570, p = 0.006) and the requirement for ventilatory support (AHR = 2.406, p = 0.013) were identified as independent risk factors for increased mortality. These findings suggest that managing conditions such as hepatorenal syndrome and providing adequate respiratory support are crucial in reducing mortality risk among AKI patients (Table 3).

Table 3: Multivariate Cox Regression Analysis of Predictors of Mortal

Variables	AHR	95% CI	p-value
Age (years)	18–30	0.48	0.221–1.043
	31–45	0.825	0.425–1.602
	46–60	0.849	0.457–1.578
Single AKI etiology	1.209	0.659–2.221	0.54
Evidence of HRS	3.57	1.453–8.769	0.006
Cardiogenic shock	0.758	0.14–4.108	0.748
Hypovolemic shock	0.72	0.191–2.714	0.627
Septic shock	0.684	0.244–1.912	0.469
Evidence of GN	0.82	0.373–1.804	0.622
Evidence of sepsis	1.988	0.989–3.993	0.054
Patient on MV	2.406	1.203–4.809	0.013
Patient on vasopressor	1.689	0.596–4.785	0.324
Presence of comorbidities	1.169	0.643–2.126	0.609
Diabetes	0.918	0.452–1.864	0.813
Protein (gm/dl)	0.965	0.742–1.256	0.793
Albumin (gm/dl)	0.887	0.637–1.236	0.48

AKI: acute kidney injury; HRS: hepatorenal syndrome; GN: glomerulonephritis; MV: mechanical ventilation; AHR: adjusted hazard ratio; CI: confidence interval. Reference group for age: ≥61 years, Reference group for AKI etiology: Multiple, Reference group for rest of the variables: Absence of the condition

The study presents a comparison of various factors associated with patient outcomes, which are categorized as complete recovery, partial recovery, or non-recovery. Several factors were found to have a significant association with these outcomes, including age, etiology, hypovolemia, hepatorenal syndrome, shock, glomerulonephritis, sepsis, KDIGO stage, mechanical ventilation, vasopressors, renal replacement therapy (RRT) requirement, comorbidities, obstetrics and gynecological disorders, serum creatinine, hemoglobin, total leucocyte count (TLC), and

serum glutamic-oxaloacetic transaminase (SGOT) levels (all with p-values less than 0.05). Following this, these factors were further analyzed using multinomial logistic regression to assess their independent contributions to the prediction of patient outcomes. In the comparison between non-recovery and complete recovery outcomes, specific factors significantly impacted patient outcomes. Hemoglobin levels and the presence of glomerulonephritis were key contributors to the likelihood of non-recovery. An increase in hemoglobin was associated with a decreased

probability of non-recovery, suggesting that higher hemoglobin levels may improve recovery chances. On the other hand, the presence of glomerulonephritis as an etiological factor increased the likelihood of non-recovery by 9.8 times, indicating that glomerulonephritis significantly worsened the prognosis and contributed to poorer patient outcomes.

Discussion

The present study found that the majority of patients were from the younger age group, which aligns with the findings of several previous studies. However, some studies have reported a significant involvement of elderly patients. In developed countries, elderly individuals tend to have a higher incidence of Acute Kidney Injury (AKI), while in developing countries, younger populations are more commonly affected. This discrepancy may be due to the different causes of AKI in these regions. In developing countries, AKI is primarily caused by infectious and environmental factors, whereas in developed countries, the elderly population experiences a higher incidence of AKI, often due to complications related to pre-existing medical conditions. Additionally, a male predominance was observed in the current study, which is consistent with previous research. However, Lee et al [8] reported a higher percentage of females (59.2%) in their study, highlighting some variability in gender distribution across different studies.

In the present study, comorbidities were observed in 27.9% of participants, with hypertension and diabetes mellitus being the most common, consistent with findings from various other studies [9,10]. The increased risk of Acute Kidney Injury (AKI) in these patients may be attributed to the presence of pre-existing conditions such as chronic kidney disease (CKD), cardiovascular diseases (including acute coronary artery syndromes), and hyperglycemic crises. Additionally, certain medications, such as intravenous contrast agents and antibiotics, can contribute to the development of AKI, further elevating the risk in patients with these comorbidities.

Most participants in this study were admitted to the nephrology and medicine departments, which aligns with findings from studies by Teo et al, Vasanth et al, and Kiran et al [4, 11, and 12]. This suggests that medical issues, rather than surgical ones, are the predominant underlying causes of Community-Acquired Acute Kidney Injury (CAAKI). However, it is important to note that potential selection bias could be introduced due to the enrollment of patients based on consultation referrals, which may limit the generalizability of the findings to the broader population.

Most of our study participants were in KDIGO stage 3, followed by stage 2 and stage 1. Abebe et

al [9], Kaaviya et al [2] Korula et al [13] also reported stage 3 as the most common KDIGO stage at which AKI diagnosis was made. Methodological variations, patient enrollment approaches, and delays in reporting or hospital referral may contribute to these discrepancies. Our reliance on referral calls to nephrology may have resulted in missing milder AKI cases, and the limited availability of baseline creatinine data influenced severity classification. In our study, a single etiology of Acute Kidney Injury (AKI) was observed in most patients, which is consistent with the findings of Teo et al [4]. Sepsis was identified as the most common cause, followed by shock, glomerulonephritis, and hypovolemia. These results align with those from other studies by Teo et al [4] and Chetlapalli et al [14]. The study highlights the significance of sepsis as a leading cause of AKI in the cohort. Overall, our research provides valuable insights into the unique characteristics and outcomes of Community-Acquired Acute Kidney Injury (CA-AKI) within the context of a developing country, further contributing to the understanding of this condition in such settings.

Our study highlights diverse drug contributors to renal impairment, with NSAIDs being the most prevalent (46.3%). This underscores the significant impact of NSAIDs on renal function, as supported by a study²³ indicating a 58% increased risk of AKI with NSAID use, emphasizing the need for heightened awareness of renal risks in clinical practice. The varying contributions of alternative medications and anti-tubercular drugs underscore the importance of evaluating multiple factors when assessing and managing drug-induced renal impairment. This emphasizes the crucial need for clinicians to remain vigilant about the potential impact of different drug classes on renal function.

Our study revealed that most patients experienced complete recovery, followed by partial recovery and non-recovery, which is consistent with the findings of González et al [15] reported recovery in 53.5% of their patients, followed by end-stage renal disease (ESRD). These findings highlight the reversible nature of Acute Kidney Injury (AKI) and emphasize the potential for prevention through early intervention and timely management. Early detection and appropriate treatment can significantly improve patient outcomes and reduce the risk of progression to more severe conditions such as ESRD.

The current study revealed several risk factors independently associated with mortality, including elderly age, multiple AKI-causing etiologies, hepatorenal syndrome, and presence of shock, glomerulonephritis, sepsis, MV requirement, vasopressor use, comorbidities, diabetes, TLC, serum protein, and albumin. Similarly, Chetlapalli et al [14] found hypotension, anemia and the need

for RRT associated with mortality. In a study by Abebe et al [9] hyperkalemia, sepsis, anemia, need for RRT, and age ≥ 60 years were found to be correlated with mortality. As per the results of Kaaviya et al [2] hypotension, mechanical ventilation, thrombocytopenia, and anuria were significantly associated with death. Lee et al [8] found factors such as elderly age, heart failure, liver disease, diuretic use, pre-admission hemoglobin, albumin, and platelet count to be significantly associated with mortality. These factors emphasize the complexity and multi-faceted nature of AKI outcomes.

Conclusion

Our study on Acute Kidney Injury (AKI) in a developing country highlights the predominance of younger patients, with infectious and environmental factors playing a significant role in the etiology of AKI. Sepsis, particularly from gastrointestinal sources, emerges as a major contributor, emphasizing the need for increased clinical awareness and preventive strategies to mitigate the potential renal impacts.

The study underscores the reversible nature of AKI, with most patients experiencing complete recovery. However, mortality rates remain substantial, which highlights the severity of the condition and the urgency of medical intervention. Additionally, the use of Nonsteroidal Anti-Inflammatory Drugs (NSAIDs) is identified as a significant risk factor for renal impairment, urging clinicians to remain vigilant about their potential renal effects, particularly in vulnerable populations.

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